

TETR ARCHs

Transforming Data Reuse in Archaeology

Deliverable 5.2

Experiment Trials

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Summary

This Deliverable 5.2, titled *Experiment Trials*, provides a report on the initial experiments developed and carried out during the first year of the TETRARCHs project. These include experiments on legacy data reuse that took place during excavations at Västra Vång (Sweden) and Toumba Serron (Greece), as well as those on eliciting responses to archaeological photographs at MOLA (UK). The experiments at each of these settings are explained and discussed in detail, before closing the deliverable with general considerations that will form the foundations for future TETRARCHs work.

Introduction: Aim of the Deliverable

This deliverable reports on the results of the experiments developed during the first year of the project. Specifically, it reports on three separate experiments, two focused on archaeological fieldwork in Sweden and Greece and one at Museum of London Archaeology (MOLA) in the UK. The experiments aimed to gain insight into the process of data reuse of archaeological records and to map the ways in which legacy data are incorporated into interpretation and employed to construct new narratives.

The **First** experiment has been developed within the activities of the Västtra Vång archaeological excavation and has been carried out in collaboration with the Blekinge Museum in Sweden. The experiment aimed to explore how field archaeologists reuse (digital) legacy data in preparation for and during the fieldwork and how the archaeological records collected during the fieldwork are reused by the museum to engage a wider audience. It also explores the creation of narratives around archaeological information for the collection of annotations that will be used to build classes for the Storytelling Data Model.

The **Second** experiment focused on the Toumba Serron research project in Greece. It involved a wide range of 3D spatial documentation techniques and aimed to assess whether the use of current graphical representation strategies and metadata was sufficient to meet research objectives and user needs. The experiment included stakeholder assessment and mapping of user needs to facilitate input from different communities and promote the co-creation of archaeological knowledge.

The **Third** experiment was developed at the Museum of London Archaeology (MOLA) and focused on the reuse of existing photographs of archaeological sites. It involves enhancing the existing metadata of these datasets to make them reusable for different stakeholders. The experiment uses a site from the MOLA archives and works with multiple user groups (archaeological specialists, creative practitioners, school children) in workshops to enrich the metadata with relevant terms and tags. The aim was to identify strategies for making these records more accessible for different purposes and to inform the development of the Storytelling Data Model.

The following sections provide a comprehensive overview of the case studies and associated experiments conducted by WP5 during the first year, along with the outcomes. These experiments were conceived as a continuation of D5.1 and were aligned with the trajectories outlined in D4.1 and D4.2. The iterative development of these experiments facilitated the identification of aspects that were overlooked in the initial fieldwork planning, leading to unexpected results.

The results, extensively discussed in the "Results & Discussion" sections, played a crucial role in pinpointing significant gaps in our approach to data collection and reuse. To enhance the reliability and relevance of these findings, the results of the experiments will undergo evaluation and refinement in closed workshops. These workshops will involve participation from local community members and critical friends who are specifically invited to provide valuable insights and challenge the methodologies employed by WP5.

1. Västra Vång

The cultural landscape of Johannishus Ronneby municipality is rich in burial grounds from the Bronze Age and Iron Age. During the Middle Ages, Blekinge County Council had its administrative centre on the ridge in Hjortsberga parish, and in the early Swedish period, the area was mainly characterised by agriculture and forestry under the ownership of the Johannishus estate.

Although it may seem obvious today that this area served as a central settlement during the Iron Age, it wasn't until 2004 that a more substantial Iron Age settlement was discovered, coinciding with the village of Västra Vång. That year, Blekinge Museum carried out an archaeological survey in the area as part of a water treatment project. The findings were so interesting that they prompted further research. This eventually led to a research project in collaboration with Södertörn University and Lund University.

Our understanding of Iron Age Vång has grown yearly since 2004. Today, the settlement, which covers an area of about 15 hectares, shows a continuous and prosperous history. The earliest traces of the Iron Age at Vång date back to the centuries before Christ, and the site retained important functions and a distinctive role within the area until the end of the Viking Age. Its importance is underlined by the ritual plateau on the central hill of the settlement.

Numerous finds at this site reflect Vång's central role in the landscape, particularly in relation to religious beliefs and associated ritual practices. Notable finds include fragments of bronze vessels, the remains of numerous glass beakers, and 69 gold foil figures known as 'guldgubbar'. The site is now an important place for the people of the Johannishus area and the municipality of Ronneby.

1.1 Excavations at Västra Vång

Over the years, [several excavation campaigns](#) have been carried out with the help and support of volunteers from the Blekinge region. The Västra Vång archaeological site is a cultural landmark in Blekinge, and Blekinge County Council, together with Blekinge Museum, have created a space where the artefacts and the history of Västra Vång are presented to the public. The fieldwork at Västra Vång, conducted by Blekinge Museum and Lund University, has used advanced digital documentation techniques from the very beginning, and the records have been made openly accessible through a 3D web-based platform developed by Lund University.

In 2004, Karlskrona Municipality started a water treatment project at Johannishus in Ronneby Municipality. In connection with this, Blekinge Museum was given the opportunity to carry out archaeological excavations along the route of the pipeline. A previously unknown and unexpectedly rich Iron Age settlement was discovered in the village of Västra Vång, where traces of houses and craft areas were found on the village's farmland, indicating a presence on the site from at least the Roman Iron Age to the Viking Age. At the same time, a small bronze mask from the Celtic cultural area was found on the smaller mound in the centre of the settlement, dating from around the time of Christ's birth. In the following years, further investigations were carried out, both in the settlement as a whole and soon on the hill. Because the cultural environment on the hill itself is so well preserved and has gradually been shown to contain almost unique finds and remains, the choice of archaeological documentation methods has been particularly careful and has been designed from the outset to provide future users with a very detailed set of data. The archaeological remains on the hill are well preserved below the surface of the turf. Georadar imagery and deeper test excavations indicate that the archaeology extends to a depth of almost one metre in some areas. The stratigraphy varies considerably depending on the location on the hill. Minor subtle changes allow us

to distinguish soil layers, with variations in the presence of burnt clay, soot and charcoal. The same variability can be observed in the types of artefacts found, which are associated with different layers.

In some cases, these layers were formed by natural deposition as the surface was used for activities or exposed to the elements. In other cases, new layers have been created by the deliberate addition of soil. On the hill in particular, this is most evident in the use of non-natural silty layers to cover specific areas, often surrounded by stone packs. In summary, these findings have contributed to our understanding of a now-lost architectural structure with ritual significance at this site.

1.2 Legacy Data Scenarios

The large datasets of archaeological records archived over the years, the presence of an active museum that was established to create a mediating space between the community and the archaeological site, and the use of advanced recording techniques made Västra Vång an ideal place to develop a first set of experiments focused on studying data reuse in archaeology and identifying recording techniques that facilitate the establishment of creative practices.

Since the first survey campaign, a number of advanced 3D spatial recording techniques have been used on-site to record detailed diachronic materials and contexts encountered during the investigations. In particular, a high-resolution 3D recording of the mound was documented using a DJI drone (X300) equipped with a lidar sensor (L1), and a more detailed recording campaign of the mound on which the site is located was undertaken using a phase-shifting laser scanner to create a high-resolution representation of the environment surrounding the excavation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Detail of the mesh acquired using the Phase shift laser scanner.

The graphic documentation was performed using image-based 3D modelling techniques to produce 3D models of contexts and (where possible) artefacts for inclusion in the 3D GIS. Once georeferenced, the 3D models were imported into the GIS and used as palimpsests for drawing the contexts and/or artefact locations using digital polylines and polygons (shapefiles).

Since 2021, the graphical and textual documentation has been integrated into the Archaeological Interactive Reporting System (AIR) and made available via the Internet by the Digital Archaeology Laboratory at Lund University, [DARKLab](#). The system is the result of a [PhD project](#) and is based on a combination of Omeka S and 3DHOP (for more information, see D5.1 and D4.2). AIR has been used in the last two years by the archaeologists working in the field to record and archive the archaeological documentation and to publish the archaeological reports of each campaign. Within the framework of TETRARCHs, we are exploring the possibility of integrating into AIR different narrative templates constructed using the archaeological datasets available in the system. In order to accomplish this task, it was necessary to identify how archaeologists and non-archaeologists reuse the data available in the system to formulate or support different interpretations (narrative construction) and to identify the limitations of the digital archive structure/model in supporting such narratives. The development of this task will also guide on how to increase the searchability of the narratives created by different users engaging with the archive.

1.3 Objectives

The excavation at Västra Vång took place from 1 to 6 May 2023. During the excavation, we used advanced 3D recording methods to ensure accurate documentation of all information. The collected data, both graphical and textual, was catalogued in the AIR system while in the field and thus made available online throughout the excavation.

A dedicated team of eight archaeologists, each with a different combination of digital and field expertise, was actively involved in this endeavour. Their contribution included fieldwork, data recording, archival processes, and pre-excavation and on-site discussions. This comprehensive methodological approach followed the structure described in D5.1, and allowed us to conduct two different experiments:

1. The first experiment focused on observing and analysing how archaeologists reused previously archived data within the system to facilitate the field excavation process.
2. The second experiment focused on the reuse of archaeological records collected during fieldwork and archived in the system, specifically investigating how the museum could use them to engage a wider audience.

Our primary aim in conducting these experiments was to address the following key issues:

- Assessing the role of advanced field documentation in archaeological practice;
- Evaluating the use of digital data during excavation, with a particular focus on how archaeologists used 3D data and the 3D archive to support their analytical and argumentative processes and theories;
- Examining the use of digital data to challenge or refine established archaeological theories;
- Assessing the potential for reusing the data stored in the archive to create narratives that resonate with a wider range of users;
- Identifying existing gaps in current archives and documentation approaches that may hinder the development of diverse narratives by different users;
- Providing WP3 with relevant evidence to assist in the formulation of new metadata to improve the accessibility of archaeological records held in the archive.

1.4 Experiment 1: Legacy Data Reuse for Archaeological Research

The efforts in WP4 (D4.1, D4.2) emphasised the necessity of determining when and under what circumstances archaeologists make use of archaeological archives to generate new knowledge. Moving beyond the traditional archaeological report, our aim was to investigate instances where the accessibility of an archive becomes a pivotal factor for a team of archaeologists in the interpretation process.

The first experiment was designed to observe and document how archaeologists, when provided with the chance to interact with a well-organised set of legacy data, repurposed it to bolster their interpretations. Prior to initiating the experiment, we outlined specific scenarios to recreate the desired dynamics, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Graphic description of the phases of Experiment 1 as described in D5.1

The initial plan, detailed in D5.1, provided an overview of the experiment. However, as mentioned in the introduction, once in the field, we had the opportunity to enhance and expand our observations and analysis. The subsequent narrative offers a comprehensive journey, covering the experiment's evolution from its original project design to its refined state in the field.

Experiment 1 involved archaeologists actively participating in the excavation at Västra Vång. This group exhibited diverse specialisations and digital skills, as elaborated in 1.1.6, below. The objectives of the experiment were threefold: (1) to evaluate the potential reuse of 3D data stored in the archaeological archive by practitioners, (2) to discern the purposes and methods of utilising the 3D data (such as for visualisation or knowledge transfer), and (3) to provide both quantitative and qualitative insights into the use of this type of media, with potential applicability to other forms of media.

Specifically, the Västra Vång experiment involved the observation and analysis of archaeologists reusing 3D data during conversations and meetings. A week prior to the excavation, the entire team gathered to deliberate on objectives and excavation strategies. Crafting an effective excavation strategy involves considering both research goals and logistical factors. Striking a balance between the desired objectives, available time, and resources is crucial in this process. In this context, having access to an archive supported by a system capable of real-time scenario simulation is immensely valuable for archaeologists. This is why, during the meeting, we utilised the AIR system, specifically developed for Västra Vång, as a supportive tool.

AIR offers online access to the complete digital excavation archive, enabling the observation of spatial relationships among artefacts and contexts recovered in various excavation campaigns. During the meeting, the system was projected onto a large screen, and multiple archaeologists accessed it on their laptops to engage in the discussion (Fig. 3). The 3D data stored in AIR played a crucial role during the meeting, serving to illustrate past excavation seasons, delineate excavation areas and

archaeological features. These 3D models were instrumental in supporting interpretations and decisions related to excavation objectives, trench positioning, and the overall excavation strategy.

As part of the experiment, the pre-excitation meeting was recorded using a 360-degree camera. Subsequent analysis of the video recordings aimed to evaluate how and when archaeologists utilized the digital archive to explore and assess various hypotheses.

The excavation employed a single context approach, with all documentation completed on-site. Graphic documentation involved a combination of image-based 3D modelling and a total station survey, enabling the georeferencing of the 3D models. Context drawings were created using polygons directly within AIR (Fig. 4). After recording, the contexts were described using the digital record sheet within AIR. This approach allowed for real-time access to the records, enabling anyone to check and immediately reuse the data in the field during the survey.

On two evenings following the excavation, the team convened to review the field strategy, discuss findings, and, crucially, compare the newly acquired records with those from prior campaigns. These sessions were recorded and analysed to comprehend how and to what extent the archival records were utilised in interpreting the fresh data. Despite spending the entire day in the field, the opportunity to visually aggregate and manipulate both old and new records during these meetings sparked extensive discussions among team members (Fig. 5). Numerous interpretative hypotheses were formulated, challenged, and refined, significantly enhancing engagement and participation across the entire team. A comprehensive quantitative analysis of the system's usage and the team's interaction with old and new data is presented in the subsequent sections.

Fig. 3: The meeting was recorded and analysed to assess the use of the digital archive for the definition of the excavation strategy.

Fig. 4: Uploading the archaeological records on-site using AIR

Fig. 5: Team members engaging using the system to explore different hypotheses

The three meeting videos were recorded on 24 April, 2 May, and 3 May. The first, which involved six archaeologists, lasted 87 minutes. Seven archaeologists participated in the two meetings recorded the evening after the excavations. The second lasted 55 minutes, and the third lasted 50 minutes.

The videos' annotations were performed using the software [Elan](#) (Fig. 6), a free annotation tool for audio and video recordings. The software allows textual annotation to audio and video recordings on multiple layers labelled 'tiers'. The tiers can be hierarchically interconnected to time chunks and annotations.

In Elan, after uploading the movie, every conversation was identified by tiers (i.e., VV2023_1 defines the first conversation that occurred in the first video, which is anchored to the time frame it occurs).

Each conversation was attributed a purpose-value based on the use of 3D scenes:

- conversation with the use of 3D models to define the trenches' location
- conversation with the use of 3D models to show/describe/measure something
- conversation with the use of 3D models to define the excavation's goals/research questions
- conversation with the use of 3D models to illustrate interpretations

- conversation with the use of 3D models to support decision-making

The conversation tiers were enriched with textual annotations that summarised the conversation.

The 3D models used in the conversations were hierarchically connected to the conversation tiers as 'child' tiers. In order to identify the 3D models used and quantify their reuse, they were also attributed tier types.

Fig. 6: Screenshot of the Elan software displaying the layout: movie frame (on the top left), annotation list (top right), audio annotation panel (bottom).

1.5 Experiment 2: Legacy Data Reuse for Narrative Creation

The second experiment involved a specific user group, consisting primarily of specialists from Blekinge Museum and collaborators from the local community who volunteered their expertise (see the next section for more details on the participants). The aims of this experiment were threefold: (1) to assess the potential for reusing data from the archaeological field archive to create narratives that resonate with a wider audience, (2) to identify existing gaps in the archaeological archives used during the excavation (based on the merging of 3DHOP and Omeka S), and (3) to provide WP3 with relevant evidence for formulating new metadata. The aim is to improve the accessibility of the archaeological records held in the archive.

The experiment focused on reusing archaeological records from fieldwork to create an interactive online narrative tailored for a diverse audience. The first step was to invite Mikael Henriksson, the field director at Blekinge Museum, to write a story focusing on specific and interesting aspects of Västra Vång. The story was aimed at visitors to the museum, and although it was based on archaeological finds and material evidence, it wasn't limited to the data stored in AIR. Once the story was developed, it was seamlessly integrated into the report layout within AIR, closely linked to the information stored in the archive (Fig. 7).

stratigraphic sequence encountered during the investigation. Individual strata, burials and finds are described and given different digital identities so that they can be distinguished in databases and used to support archaeological interpretation. The end result is a coherent digital information chain linked to databases and high-resolution images of trenches, strata and finds. The archaeological evidence is gone forever, but the computer can simulate the progress of the investigation through the various stages. With a consistent working method, it is then possible to piece together puzzles from different seasons of fieldwork, as information and 3D photogrammetry can be merged into a larger whole.

Fig. 7: Screenshot of the online system displaying the story created by the Blekinge Museum personnel and incorporated in AIR

Fig. 8: Graphic description of the field experiment phase 2

Once the final version of the [Vångakullen and archaeology story](#) was approved, we outlined the workshop strategy and structure to gather essential information for constructing the Storytelling Data Model in WP3.

With assistance from Mikael Henriksson at Blekinge Museum, participants were selected from museum personnel and the local community of volunteers. Participants received a web link to access the story along with instructions on using the system, and were requested to review the story before the workshop.

The workshop, held at Blekinge Museum on 7 November, drew a diverse group of experts and volunteers, with the University of Antwerp recording the session (Fig. 9).

Following an explanation of the experiment, a brief demo of the interactive narrative system was conducted, collectively reviewing key components such as text organisation, the interactive canvas, and the connection with archaeological "raw data." After the introduction, printed copies of the story and associated questions were distributed to participants.

The questions were the following:

1. When first reading this story, try to take note of what words or phrases you think of after each paragraph - no need to think long about it, whatever comes first to your mind!
2. What other keywords do you associate with this story? Does it evoke any feeling memory?
3. If you were to make this story easier to find through online search, what tags would you add?

Fig. 9: Picture from the workshop at Blekinge Museum

1.6 Participants

In the 2023 field season, the TETRARCHs team were represented on-site by Nicolò Dell'Unto and Paola Derudas (Lund University), The excavation team was composed of eight excavators:

Åsa Berggren (Lund University), Nicolò Dell'Unto (Lund University), Paola Derudas (Lund University), Danilo Marco Campanaro (Lund University), Domenica Dininno (Lund University) Andreas Svensson, (Sydsvensk arkeologi), Mikael Henriksson (Blekinge Museum), Mikael Fauvelle (Lund University).

Experiment 2 was developed by Paola Derudas (Lund University), Mikael Henriksson (Blekinge Museum) and Aida Fadioui (University of Antwerp). The Blekinge Museum user group consisted of 12 people, including pedagogues, conservators, collection managers, caretakers, communication managers and volunteers from the local community who are involved in various ways in archaeological activities in the region.

The participants fall into the TETRARCHs audience mapping as defined in WP2 (D2.2) and in the case of this set of experiments, include the following categories.

specialists - field:

- excavators
- archaeological-technical professionals (i.e. whose specialism is not a period of time, site or artefact type but an archaeological method, e.g. GIS, landscape etc.)
- researchers of TETRARCHs
- researchers connected to specific archaeological sites

specialists - PX:

- archaeological photography experts
- archaeological data processing experts
- archaeological data curators (online, offline)

specialists - trainee:

- volunteers in archaeological sites

specialists - educators:

- museum professionals (e.g. guides, curators)
- pedagogical units at museums
- archaeological site guides

archaeological public impact experts:

- communications specialists, including those generating press, media and social media communications, as well as graphic design solutions (e.g. project logos) - see below

1.7 Results & Discussion

This section reports the results of the experiments carried out during the Västra Vång research campaign. The text provides information on the analytical methods used by the research team and includes considerations on the direction to be taken in future field campaigns.

As stated above, observing several ways in which 3D models were used in the conversations in the different meetings was possible. For this reason, different purpose values were assigned to sort conversations. It was interesting to observe that 3D models often supported conversations with multiple purposes. This information is displayed and discussed below.

Experiment 1

Pre-excavation meeting (24-04-2023)

In this session, a total of 33 conversations were recorded and annotated, and 60 3D models were used to support the conversations. We documented sixteen instances of "1-value purpose conversations" (aimed at defining trenches' location, showing/describing/measuring something, defining excavation goals/research questions, illustrating interpretations, and supporting decision-making). In these conversations, 3D models were utilised 29 times. Additionally, we collected thirteen instances of "2-value purpose conversations" (involving actions like showing,

describing, measuring something and illustrating interpretations; showing, describing, measuring something and supporting decision-making; defining trenches' location and illustrating interpretations). In these conversations, 3D models supported them 31 times (refer to Table 1 for details).

Use of 3D models in the conversations	conversation amount	conversation value	3D models used
3D models used to define trenches' location	2	1	4
3D models used to show/describe/measure something	6	1	10
3D models used to define excavation's goals/research questions	5	1	9
3D models used to illustrate interpretations	3	1	6
3D models used to support decision-making		1	
3D models used to show/describe/measure something; 3D models used to illustrate interpretations	8	2	20
3D models used to show/describe/measure something; 3D models used to support decision-making	4	2	10
3D models used to define trenches' location; 3D models used to illustrate interpretations	1	2	1
3D models used to show/describe/measure something; 3D models used to illustrate interpretations; 3D models used to support decision-making		3	
no 3D models	3		
no conversation definition	1		
total	33		60

Table 1: Analytical representation of archaeologists' reuse of 3D data in the pre-excavation conversation during the meeting held on 24-04-2023.

Post-excavation meeting (02-05-2023)

The first post-excavation meeting was recorded after the second day of excavation, on 2 May. During this meeting, the participants held 25 conversations using 51 3D models.

We recorded fifteen instances of “1-value purpose conversations”, in which 3D models were used 36 times (to show/describe/measure something; to illustrate interpretations; to support decision-making), eight instances of “2-value purpose conversations” (to show, describe, measure something and illustrate interpretations; define trenches' location and illustrate interpretations), in which 3D models were used 36 times, and two instances of “3-value purpose conversations”, in which nine 3D models were employed (to show, describe, measure something, illustrate interpretations and support decision-making) (see Table 2).

Use of 3D models in the conversations	conversation amount	conversation value	3D models used
3D models used to define trenches' location		1	0
3D models used to show/describe/measure something	9	1	26
3D models used to define excavation's goals/research questions		1	0
3D models used to illustrate interpretations	5	1	9
3D models used to support decision-making	1	1	1
3D models used to show/describe/measure something; 3D models used to illustrate interpretations	8	2	6
3D models used to show/describe/measure something; 3D models used to support decision-making		2	
3D models used to define trenches' location; 3D models used to illustrate interpretations		2	
3D models used to show/describe/measure something; 3D models used to illustrate interpretations; 3D models used to support decision-making	2	3	9
no 3D models			
no conversation definition			
total	25		51

Table 2: Analytical representation of archaeologists' reuse of 3D data in the post-excavation conversation during the meeting held on 02-05-2023.

Post-excavation meeting (03-05-2023)

On 3 May, the final session was recorded. Archaeologists engaged in 27 conversations, and 3D models were used 42 times to support these interactions.

We recorded nineteen instances of “1-value purpose conversations” (to show/describe/measure something; to illustrate interpretations; to support decision-making), in which 3D models were used 25 times, four instances of “2-value purpose conversations” (to show, describe, measure something and illustrate interpretations), in which 3D models supported them 15 times, and two instances of “3-value purpose conversations” (to show/describe, measure something, illustrate interpretations and support decision-making), in which nine 3D models were employed (see Table 3).

Use of 3D models in the conversations	conversation amount	conversation value purpose	3D models used
3D models used to define trenches' location		1	0
3D models used to show/describe/measure something	10	1	12
3D models used to define excavation's goals/research questions		1	0
3D models used to illustrate interpretations	8	1	12
3D models used to support decision-making	1	1	1
3D models used to show/describe/measure something; 3D models used to illustrate interpretations	4	2	15
3D models used to show/describe/measure something; 3D models used to support decision-making		2	
3D models used to define trenches' location; 3D models used to illustrate interpretations		2	
3D models used to show/describe/measure something; 3D models used to illustrate interpretations; 3D models used to support decision-making	1	3	2
no 3D models	3		
no conversation definition	1		
total	27		42

Table 3: Analytical representation of archaeologists' reuse of 3D data in the post-excavation conversation during the meeting held on 03-05-2023.

Data reuse summary and conclusions

In total, archaeologists engaged in 85 conversations across the three sessions, utilizing 3D models a total of 153 times. Out of these conversations, we identified the value purposes for 78 instances. The majority of conversations (50) fell into the "1-value purpose" category, where 3D models were used 89 times. The primary use of 3D models in these cases was to show, describe, or measure something (25 times, involving 48 models) and/or to illustrate interpretations. We documented 29 instances of "2-value purpose conversations," where archaeologists used 41 3D models. In twenty cases, these models were used to show, describe, or measure something and to illustrate interpretations; in four instances, 10 3D models were employed to show, describe, or measure something and support decision-making, and in one occasion, a single 3D model was used to define trenches' location and illustrate interpretations. Additionally, there were three instances of "3-value purpose conversations," utilizing 12 3D models to show, describe, or measure something, illustrate interpretations, and support decision-making (refer to Charts 1 and 2 for details).

Chart 1: the chart illustrates how archaeologists reused 3D models in all the conversations that took place as part of Experiment 1

In conclusion, our data shows:

- **Usage of 3D Models:** The extensive use of 3D models (153 times) indicates their pivotal role in supporting and enhancing archaeological discussions and activities.
- **Multi-value Purposes:** Out of the conversations analysed, specific value purposes were identified for 78 instances. This suggests a clear understanding and categorisation of the intentions behind using 3D models during these interactions.

- **Dominant "1-value Purpose" Conversations:** The majority of conversations (50 instances) were categorised as "1-value purpose," emphasising a focused use of 3D models for specific objectives. In these cases, the primary purposes included showing, describing, or measuring something (25 times, involving 48 models) and illustrating interpretations (16 times).
- **Versatility in "2-value Purpose" Conversations:** The occurrence of 29 instances of "2-value purpose" conversations highlights the versatility of 3D models, serving dual objectives such as showing, describing, or measuring something and illustrating interpretations.
- **Varied Use in "3-value Purpose" Conversations:** In three instances of "3-value purpose" conversations, 3D models were employed for a combination of showing, describing, or measuring something, illustrating interpretations, and supporting decision-making.

Chart 2: Reuse of 3D models in conversations based on the value purposes identified by combining the information from the three meetings: in yellow the "1-value purpose" conversations; in green "2-value purpose" conversations; in blue "3-value purpose" conversations

Overall, these findings underscore the multi-faceted utility and the possibility of reuse of 3D models in archaeological discussions, ranging from singular focused purposes to more complex and layered applications in decision-making and interpretation. The specific breakdown in Charts 1 and 2 provides a detailed overview of the distribution and purposes of 3D model usage in these conversations.

Experiment 2

The second experiment took place at the Blekinge Museum on 7 November. The primary goal was to gather information for developing a new ontology for WP3. This collaborative initiative included the University of Antwerp and focused on obtaining feedback, in the form of concise descriptions and keywords, for an online archaeological narrative crafted by the leading archaeologists at Västra Vång.

The narrative, organised into paragraphs, was accompanied by digital materials such as images and 3D models directly sourced from the excavation archive. Participants received these materials in advance and had a few days to review and explore them. During the workshop, their task was to annotate observations, expressed as brief sentences, and provide keywords for each paragraph.

The survey results were subsequently compiled and entered into a spreadsheet (Table 4). Despite the anonymisation of the surveys, we retained participants' roles in relation to the results. The table allows for the identification of keywords associated with each section of the story, along with emotional memories conveyed by some participants. For those who wrote in Swedish, an English translation, completed by a native Swedish speaker, was provided. Ultimately, the spreadsheet file was shared with Aida Fadioui for analysis.

Participants were asked to annotate the text with their instinctual reactions (quick association). They were also asked to reflect on what tags could make this story more findable through online searches. The goal of this part of the experiment was to collect keywords and/or key phrases which are then fed into the “keyword pool” that forms the basis on which the Storytelling Data Model (D3.2) is built.

Some of the keywords collected can be mapped to existing metadata categories, like features, time periods, or find types (not included in Table 5). For the others, new classes are created, and the annotations themselves serve as a first draft of vocabularies for the data model.

A lot of the classes outlined in this experiment also appeared in the MOLA experiments, such as characteristics of the media (in this case, text and 3D models as opposed to photography), feeling/emotion, corporeal elements, and features of the environment or the find (usually involving affective language). A category that had not emerged previously relates to community and outreach (Table 5). The annotations made fall under three different types: on the story itself, on the text and/or 3D models and pictures, and relating to the format in a more general matter. The annotations contain a lot of affective language, whether they relate to the story itself or its format (e.g: “wonderful mix of techniques, feels new and futuristic” - on the mix of text and 3D models).

Some annotations also make a reference to the different specialities in archaeology (such as anthracology or archaeobotany), and one even underlines the necessity of using the help of different specialists to better understand the finds and the site; this is a trend that has also been observed with our partners from memory institutions and organisations.

These annotations will be pooled with those from the other experiments and analysed in order to build classes for the Storytelling Data Model that are tailored to the different audiences we are working with. The annotations categorised as “vocabulary” will be sieved through and changed so they can constitute a practical thesaurus.

background	key words paragraph 1	key words paragraph 2	key words paragraph 3	key words paragraph 4	key words paragraph 5	key words paragraph 6
	so near the surface	wonderful with 3D and the mix of the data from excavation together	interesting with different interpretations, start the fantasy and back again	starts even more the imagination	interesting that the conservation helps the interpretation	the importance... att jämföra med andra fyndplatse(to match with other find sites)
	"sjunken kyrka" lager ("sunken church" layer,)	data 3D	lack of data	komplex	reconstruction	förändring untouched?
	archaeological layers	technique to keep the hill archaeologically intact	history that can't be seen	Celtic/Roman finds	difficulties of conservation. What materials are valued? Spread about Vång	rearranged remains
excavation, iron Age settlement, bronze mask, finds, preserved, method	stratigraphy, layers	documented 3D, digital photography	house, pollen, posthole	mask celtics, Roman, cauldron, ritual building	3D artefacts, reconstructing status of settlement	rearranged the stratigraphy, understanding
bra background info, utgrävning, historisk saknas (good background info, excavation, historical missing)	bild på exempel av stratigrafin (picture of example of the stratigraphy)	mer om 3D photo utförs (more about 3D photo is performed)	rekonstruktion av hur byggvaden har vett ut? bild (reconstruction of how the construction wade has looked? picture)	bild exempel jämförande fynd? (bild exempel jämförande fynd?)	mer bilder (more photos)	mer bilder (more photos)
spännande, vill veta mere, mystiskt, blir ny fiken (exciting, wanting to know more, mysterious, getting curious)	vill veta vilken typ av föremål; vill veta varför, spännande, mystiskt (want to know what type of item; want to know why, exciting, mysterious)	känns nytt och tekniskt, framtid (feels new and technological, future)	hur såg husen ut (what did the houses look like); varför? (why?)	vill veta mer om fynden, vilken typ av fynd? blir nyfiken (want to know more about the findings, what kind of findings? gets curious)	vilken typ av vapen? (what kind of weapon?)	vill veta mer om dessa!! (want to know more about this -gold foil figures)
intro, make the reader interested and read further	mystery	technology	house shape?	travels, copies	corrosion	gold
	the site and deep of interest	strategy of collecting data	interpreting the date	completing specific data	use specialists to understand	how other finds complete the understanding, spread data and knowledge to others/public guldgubbar (gold foil figures), plundering
Iron Age, hill, unexpected	technical, complicated, hard to interpret	digital, re-create, arkeologik metod (archaeology methods)	building	vessels, fragments	3D, degraded weapons	1. pedagogy, local community /2. continuity, interest in the site/knowledge of the site
geographically where?	1. landscape, Joannishus, ancient/ 2. exciting, difficult, community	1. involvement, care, digital /2. opportunities, easy pedagogy, university	exhibition, stories, people /2. building and landscape focus. Where are the people?	1. continuity, stratigraphy, presenting /2. exhibit?, reconstruction	1. exhibition, Mosegaard /2. complexity, what hapened?	
	Beskrivning av plats- stratigrafi; hill, walls, georadar, stratigraphy, artefacts, layer	teknologi och teknik arbets metod (technology and technics, working method), methods, strata, finds	remains, houses, pollen, charcoal, context	find, period, bronze	find placering (finds position), 3D models, artefacts, fragments, weapons	contexts, finds
Iron Age, Joannishusåsen, bronze mask	georadar images, lost building, jord (soil) material	digital photography, 3D models, #simulate different seasons	walls, size of the house, construction, materials	finds 2013, ritual building, artefact	reconstructing, sword parts, återskapa föremål (recreate objects)	artefacts in layer, posthole structure
Exploateringsarkeologi, boplat, järnålder feeling: 2004...(Exploitation archaeology, settlement, Iron Age feeling: 2004...)	Stratigrafi, fynd, kultus; feeling: complexity (Stratigraphy, finds, cult house; feeling: complexity)	Handrensning, dokumentation, digitalarkeologi feeling: patience...(Hand cleaning, documentation, digital archeology feeling: patience...)	Stenpackningar, huslämningar, jordprover feeling: hopeful (Stone packings, house remains, soil samples feeling: hopeful)	fragment, kopparlegering, bronskittlar feeling: overwhelming (fragments, copper alloy, bronze kettles feeling: overwhelming)	Fyndmodeller, forskning, rekonstruktioner feeling: annoyance (Find models, research, reconstructions feeling: annoyance)	Lösfynd, depositioner, störningar feeling: tiredness (Loose finds, deposits, disturbances feeling: tiredness)

Table 4: Analytical representation of the comments and keywords identified in the story's sections by the workshop participants

Characteristics of the text/model (affective language)	good background info, technical language - hard to interpret, wonderful with 3D and the mix of the data from excavation, starts the imagination
Media type/format	georadar images, 3D model, digital photography
Feeling/emotion	exciting, mysterious, getting curious, unexpected, difficult, feels new, patience, hopeful, overwhelming, complexity, annoyance, tiredness
Features characteristics/find or environment interpretation	sunken church, lost building, cult house, travels (finds from different geographical locations/cultures), copies, ritual building, corrosion, degraded weapons, disturbances, landscape,
Outreach/community	community, care, easy pedagogy, spread data and knowledge to others/public, local community, use specialists to understand,
Physical sensations/corporeal elements, human interaction	history that can't be seen, rearranged remains, copies, plundering, travels, hand cleaning
Archaeological process	interpretation, conservation helps the interpretation, reconstruction, matching/comparing with other sites, other finds complete the understanding
Location	so near the surface,
Linked disciplines	charcoal (anthracology), pollen (archaeobotany), use specialists to understand

Table 5: identified keywords first classification. In blue classes identified in previous experiments, in orange new classes that manifested in this experiment.

2. Toumba Serron

The Late Neolithic village site of Toumba Serron (c. 5300-4500 B.C.), located in Central Macedonia, Greece, is the focus of the Toumba Serron Research Project. Positioned near the Strymon River, a critical conduit between the northern Aegean Sea and the Balkan hinterland, the site is a pivotal point for examining the material and social landscapes of a Late Neolithic community and enables comparative analysis with other prehistoric communities in the region.

Exploring stakeholder (re)user needs at the site of Toumba Serron offers unique opportunities to test new methodologies for archaeological data collection, management, and reuse. This will feed into the broader TETRARCHs objective of creating more 'just and equitable' narratives about the past through innovative data practices.

As an integral part of the TETRARCHs project at Toumba Serron, we will carry out a comprehensive 'localised' stakeholder evaluation and investigate the potential for the project's data (re)use by those stakeholders, with a specific focus upon its reuse in storytelling. As such, this specific aspect of the Toumba Serron case-study aims to identify various stakeholders and understand their interactions and connections with the site. By evaluating their interests, we hope to create a framework for data reuse that encourages engaging and meaningful storytelling around Toumba Serron's archaeological heritage.

2.1 Scenario Description

This scenario will deploy image-based modeling techniques as part of a digital workflow at an excavation/survey field project centered upon a Neolithic village in northern Greece as part of a digital field data acquisition workflow. The Toumba Serron Research Project already includes a complimentary ethnographic study which may offer a potential environment to conduct initial stakeholder evaluations and illicit feedback from those stakeholders on the methods deployed as well as fostering an inclusive environment to engage in participatory approaches and the co-creation of archaeological knowledge about the site. Through this experiment, it is possible to identify several outputs. For example, (1) the 3D excavation sequence produced in the field and made available through a 3D web visualisation system could be used by the ethnographer to support her work with the community. (2) the same datasets could be used to map how information on the ongoing excavation is transferred from archaeologists working in the field to archaeologists working in the laboratory (or in different trenches). Through these experiments, it would be possible to assess the extent of this dataset to be reused for transferring knowledge.

By developing this experiment, it could be possible to understand if the graphic representation currently produced on-site is sufficiently representative to achieve the goals set by the project and if additional parameters should be considered when making the models. In addition, this experiment would also assess if the metadata used for describing the 3D models are enough to support knowledge transfer.

The Toumba Serron Research Project is a young project, only commencing in 2019 (with fieldwork only commencing in earnest post-pandemic in 2022) and as such its data acquisition timeline has run largely in parallel with TETRARCHs. That said, the data collected in the first season has had to be consolidated into the AIR system (and might technically be regarded as a form of legacy data). This activity formed part of the digital strategy for the 2023 season (see below).

2.2 Objectives

By exploring stakeholder (re)user needs, optimising the data acquisition workflow, and creating inclusive and accessible tools for exploring the data relating to the site the Toumba Serron Research Project offers unique opportunities to test new methodologies for archaeological data collection, stewardship, and reuse. This will feed into the broader TETRARCHs objective of creating more 'just and equitable' narratives about the past through innovative data practices.

As such this first season of TETRARCHs work at Toumba Serron has had two key objectives:

- 1) Firstly, the project has sought to optimise the digital recording workflow on the site and finalise the digitisation of the projects 2022 data so that it can be integrated into the tools that TETRARCHs is developing to manage and disseminate data for reuse by multiple project stakeholders.
- 2) Secondly, work was begun to try to identify and characterise those (re)users as part of a comprehensive project stakeholder evaluation that will help to shape the development of these digital tools in order that they may facilitate wider creative reuse of the project's data.

2.3 Participants

In the 2023 field season the TETRARCHs Team were represented on site by James Taylor, Holly Wright, Helen Goodchild and Benedict Dyson (University of York), Nicolò Dell'Unto and Paola Derudas (Lund University) and Aida Fadioui (University of Antwerp).

2.4 Methodology

The TETRARCHs team prioritised the integration and customisation of the AIR system for optimal data management:

- **AIR Customisation:** A comprehensive review of the AIR data model was undertaken, tailoring it to fit the unique requirements of the Toumba Serron project and its stakeholders, which at this stage mainly included archaeologists as 'Domain Specialists' and the Eforia as custodians of the site among others.
- **Database Setup:** Before excavation activities commenced, dedicated database items were created for each investigation campaign and area to ensure organised and efficient recording.
- **Daily Documentation:** During excavations, archaeologists were documenting on AIR daily, capturing detailed metadata for each 3D model, context, and artefact. This was further emphasised by the consistent usage of unique identifiers for every item.

Fig. 10: Screenshot of the Toumba Serron Research Project’s Archaeological Interactive Report landing page.

To complement the AIR setup:

- **3D Documentation:** All contexts on-site underwent 3D documentation using image-based modelling. These were processed through Agisoft Metashape, geo-referenced, and converted for seamless online visualisation in AIR using 3DHOP.
- **Contextual Linking:** Tools like the annotation tool were employed for enhanced graphical representation of contexts, which were linked directly to their corresponding 3D models.
- **Artefact Registration:** Streamlining was achieved by registering artefacts via Excel, followed by importing them through the CSV import module in Omeka-S after thorough semantic mapping checks.

Through these measures, the team was able to develop a centralised, precise, and easily accessible digital workflow, ensuring efficient and comprehensive data management for the Toumba Serron project.

Fig. 11: Digitising a context into the Archaeological Interactive Report, 3D model is displayed on the right, single context recording information on the left.

2.5 Stakeholder Evaluation

As an integral part of the TETRARCHs project at Toumba Serron, the project is seeking to carry out a comprehensive ‘localised’ stakeholder evaluation and investigate the potential for the project’s data (re)use by those stakeholders; with a specific focus upon its reuse in storytelling. This will guide the ongoing development of Toumba Serron’s instance of AIR and other digital data stewardship tools, and help TETRARCHs to create controlled vocabularies and data structures that can facilitate wide, inclusive and creative reuse of the project data.

This specific aspect of the Toumba Serron case-study aims to identify various stakeholders and understand their interactions and connections with the site. By evaluating their interests, we hope to create a framework for data reuse that encourages engaging and meaningful storytelling around Toumba Serron's archaeological heritage.

This year the TETRARCHs team worked closely with the TSRPs ethnographer (Ioanna Antoniadou) to focus upon the following tasks:

- **Understand the existing body of research:** To avoid duplication of work by reviewing existing studies into the site’s communities and stakeholders. This also ensures that the TETRARCHs team does not ask stakeholders for information they've already provided.
- **Analyse local demographic data:** Examine data provided by local or national government bodies, charities, NGOs, or other organisations to better understand the local populace's characteristics and potential interest in the site.
- **Identify and map local organisations:** Conduct online and map searches to identify local businesses, community organisations, government bodies, media outlets, and cultural institutions. Understand their potential interest in the site and explore possible ways they

might wish to interact with the site (these stakeholders will be mapped to TETRARCHs core audiences). Local Toumba Serron stakeholders could include but are not limited to:

- **Local businesses:** Shops, restaurants, hotels, and tour operators could all have an interest in the archaeological site.
- **Community organisations:** Local clubs, societies, schools, and religious institutions could be interested in using the site for educational or cultural purposes.
- **Local government bodies:** Departments or councils focusing on education, tourism, culture, and heritage might have an interest in the site.
- **Local media:** Local newspapers, TV stations, and bloggers might be interested in stories about the site.
- **Cultural institutions:** Museums, libraries, and art galleries in the area might be interested in collaborations or events connected to the site.

This work remains ongoing during the off-season and in preparation for the 2024 field season, the project will seek to:

- **Assess the site's potential 'value' for different selected groups:** Based on the information gathered and in collaboration with the project ethnographer, assess what 'value' the Toumba Serron site carries for the identified groups. There are various types of value that we may explore here, for example (but not limited to):
 - Academic and Research Value
 - Cultural and Heritage Value
 - Preservation and Conservation Value
 - Economic and Social Value
 - Exhibition and Cultural Value
- **Design meaningful interactions:** Develop potential activities or events for these groups that facilitate storytelling and data reuse in ways that meet their needs.

2.6 Results & Discussion

It should be noted at this point that TETRARCHs activity at Toumba Serron is ongoing and scheduled to play out over three full seasons. As such there are currently no conclusive results at this stage. It is anticipated that these will be collated and written up in the last year of the TETRARCHS project.

2.7 Timeline for Completion of Work at Toumba Serron

The goal of future TETRARCHs activity at Toumba Serron is to develop ways to incorporate new forms of data and metadata optimised for wider reuse into the Toumba Serron dataset, and continue to develop and streamline 3D/Hybrid digital data acquisition workflows in order to efficiently feed data into the AIR system, thereby creating an open and interoperable system that is fully accessible for any creative stakeholder reuse needs.

There are two strands of development and assessment planned at Toumba Serron:

Strand 1: Optimisation and Integration of AIR System

1.1 Optimise Data Input into AIR

Time: Autumn 2023 - Spring 2024

Deliverable: A form that maps to TSRP recording form.

Dependencies: Collaboration with the AIR development team.

Tasks:

- A. Work with the AIR development team to streamline data input.
- B. Align input forms with TSRP requirements.

1.2 Create Output Packages in AIR

Time: Ongoing up to Spring/Summer 2025

Dependencies: Completion of 1.1, consideration of 18-month lead-in time for ARIADNE integration.

Tasks:

- A. Develop GIS ready outputs for further analysis.
- B. Create 'Archive-ready' outputs with metadata for the Archaeology Data Service.
- C. Make 'ARIADNE-ready' outputs for integration into higher-level infrastructure (e.g. ARIADNE Plus).

Strand 2: Assess TSRP Stakeholder Needs

2.1 Stakeholder Mapping Exercise

Time: Autumn 2023

Deliverable: Comprehensive evaluation of stakeholder needs.

Dependencies: Collaboration with the TSRP ethnographer.

Tasks:

- A. Collaboratively assess stakeholder needs.
- B. Prioritise key user groups for a data (re)user survey.

2.2 Development of AIR Reporting & Visualisation Tools

Time: Spring 2024 - Summer 2024 (Field Season July)

Deliverable: Methodology for (re)user survey and tested AIR reuse tools.

Dependencies: Completion of 2.1

Tasks:

- A. Identify priority stakeholders and develop the methodology for the (re)user survey.
- B. Implement the (re)user survey during the TSRP Field Season.
- C. Test AIR reuse tools during the TSRP Study Season.

Final Report

Time: End of TETRARCHs October 2025

Deliverable: Comprehensive report on all project activities and results.

Note on Dependencies

Consider that ARIADNE integration has a 1-year to 18-month lead-in time, depending on demand. This should be taken into account when planning the timeline for the output packages.

2.8 Expanded Timeline for TETRARCHs Long Term Plan

Autumn 2023

- **Strand 1**
 - Begin work with the AIR development team to optimise data input.
 - Start developing a form that maps to the TSRP recording form.
- **Strand 2**
 - Commence stakeholder mapping exercise in collaboration with the TSRP ethnographer.
 - **(Key Meeting:** Ongoing Zoom meetings with JST, HW, LF, IF & IA)
 - Complete comprehensive stakeholder evaluation (**Key Deliverable**).

Winter 2023 - Spring 2024

- **Strand 1**
 - Continue to develop AIR-TSRP data input form.
 - Begin preparations for AIR output tools.
 - **(Key Meeting:** AIR Dev. Team, ADS & Linked Data Experts - York)
- **Strand 2**
 - Identify priority stakeholders based on evaluation.
 - **(Key Meeting:** Zoom meeting with JST, HW, LF, IF & IA)
 - Develop methodology for (re)user survey.

Summer 2024 (TSRP Field Season in July)

- **Strand 1**
 - Ongoing development of AIR output tools.
- **Strand 2**
 - Implement (re)user survey during TSRP Field Season.
 - Test AIR reuse tools during the TSRP Study Season (**Key Deliverable**).

Autumn 2024 - Spring 2025

- **Strand 1**

- Finalise and test GIS, Archive, and ARIADNE-ready outputs.
- Adjust development in consideration of ARIADNE's 1-year to 18-month lead-in time.

- **Strand 2**

- Analyse (re)user survey data.
- Continue to refine AIR reporting and visualisation tools based on user feedback.

Summer 2025

- **Strand 1**

- Complete the development of AIR output tools as per Strand 1 (**Key Deliverable**).

- **Strand 2**

- Finalise development of specialised reuse tools for non-domain experts.

End of TETRARCHs October 2025

- **Final Report**

- Compile and report on all activities, findings, and deliverables (**Key Deliverable**).

Notes:

- The dependencies between the tasks have been considered in the timeline, ensuring that each phase builds upon the previous ones.
- The consideration for ARIADNE's lead-in time is integrated into the Strand 1 timeline.

3. MOLA: Experimenting with Archaeological Photographs

3.1 Site Description

The Walbrook area is located in central London, UK and is the site of, among others, Roman layers of habitation, adjacent to the Walbrook and Thames rivers (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12: The area of the MOLA excavations where the photographs of the experiment were taken. Images source: [MOLA 2017: 2](#).

Fig. 13: Excavations in 1954. Photography © Museum of London.

Fig. 14: Head of Mithras, as found in 1954. Photography © Museum of London.

These layers first became apparent under later buildings during World War II, when bombing caused extensive destruction in London. This, nevertheless, made possible the excavation of a Roman temple in the Walbrook area in the 1950s (1952-1954, Fig. 13). When it was being excavated, crowds of people were drawn to the site seeking a glimpse at the archaeology and highlighting wider public interest in the excavations. One of the discoveries made was the head of a statue of the Roman god Mithras (ca. 200 CE, Fig. 14). It was found on the last planned day of the excavation and helped excavators identify the temple as having been dedicated to Mithras (a mithraeum). It is not certain exactly what he symbolised, but we know light played a part in his cult and killing a bull was part of his mythical story.

Because of development following WWII, the temple of Mithras was moved and partly reconstructed in the 1960s (1961-1962) 100m from its original location. It was removed in 2011 and was eventually reconstituted in its current position (under the Bloomberg corporate offices as part of the public cultural offering, [London Mithraeum Bloomberg SPACE](#)) through systematic research and recording by MOLA.

Fig. 15: Indicative finds. a) amber bead in the shape of a gladiator's helmet, b) leather shoe, c) stylus tablet <WT6>, bearing one of the three earliest references to Londinium. All photography © MOLA.

In 2010-2014, Museum of London Archaeology (MOLA) continued the excavations (Fig. 16a). New buildings were to be constructed for the Bloomberg headquarters near Cannon Street, Mansion House and Bank stations, and MOLA cleared the ground for these. [At the archaeological site](#), close to

the Walbrook stream, a number of other structures were also found, including wells, walls, fences, earthworks, as well as an array of artefacts. The latter included utilitarian pieces (e.g. buckles, bells, vases, lamps, etc.), an amber bead in the shape of a gladiator's helmet (Fig. 15a), but also artefacts uniquely preserved in the mud, such as several leather shoes (Fig. 15b) and other pieces of attire. A remarkable body of artefacts that make the site exceptional, apart from the identification of the temple itself, is that of inscriptions on wooden stylus tablets, some with surviving traces of wax and containing some of the earliest written testimonies of the toponym Londinium (Fig. 15c; the inscriptions are published in their own [dedicated volume](#)). Today, the reconstructed temple of Mithras lies protected in the [basement of the Bloomberg building](#) in central London (EC4N 8AA) (Fig. 16b). It can be visited throughout the week and school engagement with the site and its artefacts is [regularly facilitated](#) (Fig. 16c).

Fig. 16: The recent state of the site. a) during excavation in the 2010s (02/01/2013), b) view of the immersive experience while at the exhibition space which hosts the reconstructed *mithraeum*, c) display wall with selected artefacts at the foyer of the exhibition space in the Bloomberg building (*Bloomberg Space*). Photography of a, b © MOLA, photography of c © Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw 2023.

3.2 Objectives and Methodology

The photography experiment based on MOLA photographs from the Walbrook/Bloomberg area excavations forms an integral part of the TETRARCHs experimentation with visual media, their metadata and the facilitation of their reuse for memory, creative and other purposes. This experiment is meant to pioneer the validity and replicability of a process through which legacy visual material and its metadata can be enriched via research with various audiences, then the outcomes analysed to inform wider recommendations pertaining to the reuse of legacy data, the creation of TETRARCHs' storytelling data model, as well as the configuration of new data, with reuse specifically built into their creation.

The procedure for this experiment was devised as comprising the following, in order:

1. identification of parameters (in terms of availability, content and metadata) of selection of a sample of photographs from MOLA excavations and of desired outcomes from experimentation;
2. selection of sample photographs;

3. identification of audiences to be involved in the pilot;
4. use of the photographs with the audiences during workshops;
5. collection of audience-generated metadata;
6. analysis and codification of the original (site excavator) and the new (audience-generated) metadata;
7. validation of the outcomes of the analysis, and codification;
8. parallel bibliographic and other academic research, in order to create a robust theoretical framework within which to do analysis and to report results;
9. recommendations about a controlled, but customisable vocabulary for future creation of archaeological images metadata, to aid [FAIR](#) practices in archaeology.

Photographic Samples

The site of MOLA's excavations of the London Mithraeum area was chosen after group consultation. Besides SP and ASG, among others making this decision were Andy Chopping (AC), then Head of Photography at MOLA, and Stu Eve (SE), then Director of Creativity at MOLA. The photographic archive from the site was preferred for its potential to yield a diversity of imagery, from mundane snapshots of archaeological features to studio-photographed 'star' finds.

Subsequently, SP and ASG collaborated with AC to amass a corpus of 50 photographs from the 2010-2014 MOLA excavations (Fig. 17). They depicted:

- a. [Finds with people](#) x 5 images
- b. [Finds without people](#) x 5 images [studio photography (e.g. Fig. 15)]
- c. [Other historic references](#) x 5 images [including photographs from the 1950s excavations (e.g. Figs. 13, 14), the 1960s reconstruction and modern museological display]
- d. [Stratigraphy with built context](#) x 5 images (e.g. Fig. 16a)
- e. [Stratigraphy with people](#) x 15 images
- f. [Stratigraphy without people](#) x 15 images

Fig. 17: The corpus (mixed, not in categories) of all 50 photos from MOLA's 2010-2014 excavations of the Walbrook/Bloomberg area, comprising the photographic experiment sample. Photography © Museum of London and MOLA.

We deliberately did not include other visual media, such as drawings, in order to make the experiment simple and to have comparable metadata derived from the same kind of interactions between user and medium. Furthermore, we agreed to include photographs of different potential for the elicitation of reactions (e.g., we postulated that a sculptural head [Fig. 14] would elicit different reactions to a trench with mud and a few stones in it). We also included photographs that we hypothesised might introduce an element of curiosity and guesswork, e.g. the photograph of the gladiator helmet bead (Fig. 15a) or that of a damaged lead pipe.

Experiment Structure

We discussed the types of reuse that this experiment ought to investigate, and devised three activities for the workshops, which we would subsequently adjust, depending on the circumstances of each group (e.g. some activities were removed to simplify the experiment for, for example, school children). The activities are described in detail below, but the logic behind them was twofold: a) to create a progression from individual engagement (Activity #1) and pair work (Activity #2) to full group work (Activity #3); b) to allow for both instinctive reactions to the visual materials (Activity #1), as well as semi-structured conditions conducive of creativity (Activities #2-3), especially storytelling (Activity #3). A typical experiment with adults was devised as being two hours long (with a break), catering for both experimentation and discussion. We calculated the software and hardware, as well as analogue materials, which would be needed for each workshop, and created online materials to be used in the course of most experiments, as outlined below. Different logistics were required for the different experiments, but the curation of metadata was adjusted accordingly.

3.3 Participants

From the outset, TETRARCHs was intended to tap into the involvement of three key audiences: domain experts, creative practitioners, and memory institutions. Taking this as a general guideline, we have, thus far, conducted experiments with three groups (further experiments with different groups may follow):

1. MOLA archaeologists and archaeology- or MOLA-related specialists (e.g. communication and outreach specialists, facilitators etc.), hosted at MOLA London and MOLA Northampton, UK, 1 pilot + 2 experiments (i.e. three workshops);
2. University students with a creative and heritage specialism, hosted at MOLA London, UK, 1 experiment;
3. Year 6 (UK primary school) pupils, aged 10-11 at a London school, UK, 1 experiment.

Numbers

- Workshop 00, 15 May 2023: test with archaeology-related staff at MOLA London, UK: 6 participants
- Workshop 01, 18 July 2023: with archaeologists + related staff at MOLA London, UK: 8 participants
- Workshop 02, 14 September 2023: with archaeologists + related staff at MOLA Northampton, UK: 8 participants
- Workshop 03, 07 November 2023: with creative students (conducted at MOLA London, UK): 15 participants
- Workshop 04, 21 November 2023: with Y6 school children (10-11 year olds) at a school in London, UK: 50 participants

Genders

Experiments 00-03 (adults)	Female	Male
00	6	0
01	3	5
02	5	3
03	13	2
Adult totals	27	10
04	50	
Child total	50	
TOTAL	87	

We deliberately did not gather data regarding the pupils who participated in Experiment 04, but there was a balance of representation overall (ca. 25 female, 25 male).

We recognise that there is a considerable gender imbalance in our adult participant sample (skewed towards female), which is due to circumstances rather than design. We will try to address this in future experiments and analysis.

Ethics

Before the start of each of the experiments, participants were given an information sheet and an ethics consent form. They chose whether to retain the information sheet (or not); they filled in the ethics form before the beginning of the experiment and returned it to SP and ASG. We ensured that the ethics forms were immediately checked to see whether they had been filled in correctly and what options of representation the participants had chosen:

- Option 1: I agree that my data are used even though I might be recognisable in photo, video and other visual and audio records (no anonymity).
- Option 2: I agree that my data are used even though I might be recognisable in photo, video and other visual and audio records, however I would prefer to be identified by the following name (pseudonym) _____.
- Option 3: I agree for my data to be used under condition of anonymity. I understand that my identity will be altered/obscured in photo, video and other visual and audio records.
- Option 4: I ask to be consulted further before my data are used in any way in this research.

In the three specialist experiments (00-02), only one person chose Option #3 (anonymity), but there was a higher proportion of this choice in Experiment 03, with one choice of Option #4 (i.e. consultation before the data are used). For Experiment 04, which involved pupils, [an adjusted information sheet](#) and ethics form were created and the latter was signed by our school liaison on behalf of this school and the pupils. All ethics forms were scanned; these and their data are being held physically and electronically separate from any other data, only accessible by SP and ASG.

3.4 Experiments 00-03 (Adults)

At the beginning of each experiment, after welcoming the participants, SP gave a short introduction to the project, its aims, as well as the aim of the experiment, using Powerpoint slides. Participants were then asked to consult the information sheet and to fill in the ethics forms before the experiment began. After the participants' permission, all experiments with adults were recorded with multiple devices (mobiles). The resulting audio files were then uploaded, automatically transcribed and partially corrected, in order to inform additional oral tagging of particular photos, and to especially reconstruct the results of Activity #3 (group storytelling).

As described above, a typical experiment comprised three activities, progressing from individual to group work and from instinctive reactions to collaborative stories.

Activity #1 (Fig. 18a)

Instructions: *Emotive Tagging: Rapidly tag 10 pictures from the Bloomberg excavations with your instinctive reactions to them (e.g., feelings, senses, memories, motivations, etc.). Feedback, discussion.*

Materials: 10 photos per person (Experiments 00-02, but 5 photos each for Experiment 03), supplied on a Jamboard (Experiments 00-02) or as printouts (Experiment 03); up to 8 of these photos were unique to each particular person. Each person had their own laptop to work on (if doing this digitally).

Workflow: Participants were given a few minutes to reflect and go through all the photographs as well as tag them with (electronic) sticky notes. A short discussion followed with volunteer

participants explaining why they attached particular tags to particular photos, as well as reflecting on which were the easiest or the most difficult to tag and why.

Positioning: People sat next to each other around a table, each working on a laptop / table space on their own.

Purpose: To gauge instinctive reactions to particular photos, regardless of whether the user knew what the depicted archaeology was or where it was found.

Fig. 18: a) Activity #1, tagging; b) Activity #2, headlines. Photography © Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw, 2023.

Activity #2 (Fig. 18b)

Instructions: *Headline Writing: In assigned pairs, create titles inspired by at least 6 of the 16 photos supplied to you. These should include:*

- 1. A headline for a newsletter read by someone who subscribes to online creative arts activities*
- 2. The title for a video game for a demographic of your choice*
- 3. The name of a podcast for someone who subscribes to history themed talks on Spotify*
- 4. A title for a YouTube video for bored teenager viewers*
- 5. The title of a new film or TV show for release on Netflix or Prime*
- 6. A title/name/headline for any other medium that appeals to *you**

Materials: 16 photos per pair, supplied on a Jamboard or as printouts, for the pair to choose up to 6. Each person had their own laptop to work on (Experiments 00-02), but the Jamboard was common between two people in the group (each pair). Therefore, both could fill in the Jamboard (or attach physical sticky notes on the printouts) simultaneously.

Workflow: Participants were put into pairs and given a few minutes to reflect and go through all the photographs as well as tag them with (electronic) sticky notes or add text to indicated sections next to each photo. A short discussion followed, with participants explaining why they attached particular tags to particular photos, as well as reflecting on which were the easiest or the most difficult to tag and why.

Positioning: People sat next to each other around a table, each working on a laptop / common table space. In Experiment 00, some people had to move around the table to form the pairs that SP and

ASG had assigned them to. From Experiment 01 onwards, we made sure that the participants initially (for Activity #1) sat in positions that would not require them to move during subsequent pair (Activity #2) and group work (Activity #3).

Purpose: To elicit creative reactions to particular photos, exchange impressions with someone else and to come up with reimagined uses of archaeological visuals in non-archaeological, popular contexts (e.g. video gaming).

Activity #3 (Fig. 19)

Instructions: *Storytelling & Storylistening*: Work in small assigned groups to arrange as many photos as you wish into a story. Then tell that story back to the group.

Materials: 50 photos per team, supplied on a Jamboard and provided as printed and laminated hard copies. Each person had their own laptop to work on, but the Jamboard was common between 3 (in Experiment 00) or 4 people (in Experiments 01-02). Therefore, any and all could fill in the Jamboard simultaneously or physically arrange any (or all) of the 50 laminated photos.

Workflow: Participants were given a few minutes to familiarise themselves with the corpus and exchange information between them (all photographs would have been seen by at least one of the participants in the room, but not necessarily by all members of each group). Participants were instructed to then create a group narrative, before sharing it with everyone in the room in a short presentation (by an individual or group of people). Some groups from Experiments 00-02 manipulated the photos online, but most chose the analogue way of delivery, with ASG subsequently reconstructing the resulting narrative. Listeners in the room were encouraged to write comments or reactions on sticky notes while the other group was presenting (mimicking Activity #1).

Positioning: As mentioned above, we facilitated the positioning of the participants around the table to enable the groups to work with minimum movement / relocation.

Purpose: To elicit creative generation of content through interaction in a group, and to gauge how photographs, hitherto individually dealt with, would work and be reinterpreted in telling a full story.

Fig 19: a) participants working on Activity #3, planning stage; b) Activity #3 during delivery. Photography © Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw, 2023.

Discussion and Feedback

Towards the end of all experiments, SP facilitated a final discussion about participants' experiences of the three activities not only in terms of content but also in terms of their design and use in the TETRARCHS project. At the very end of each experiment with adults, we asked participants to fill in a feedback form (Fig. 20), which we then took into consideration in the design of the subsequent experiments. This form was online for Experiments 00-02 and hard copy in Experiment 03.

Section 1 of 12

MOLA Photo Pilot - Experiment Two - Specialists, 14 September 2023

Have we lived up to our values? <https://www.tetrarchs.org/index.php/values/>. How can we do better as we move forward?

Q1. I felt I could be courageous at today's workshop. *

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

Fig 20: Screenshot of the beginning of the final feedback form for Experiment 02.

Overall Experiment Logistics

The experiments themselves were conducted smoothly and proved very collegial and productive. The logistics behind conducting the experiments, however, were challenging in terms of calculating workflow and dealing with some technical problems. For example, we needed enough laptops for all participants and we prepared Jamboards and survey links ahead of time, logging in to all laptops ahead of some experiments, so that each participant could click on links in the order in which they needed to conduct the activities and fill in the forms. This created technical complexities which we were able to resolve in the moment, although with some disruption. For Experiment 03, because of the size of the group which meant we could not run the experiment on laptops, we produced additional analogue materials (e.g. two additional decks of the photo corpus) and created analogue equivalents of the electronic folders for each of the activities. The latter were used to house the metadata generated by a) the individuals, b) the pairs, and c) the groups. The carefully planned logistical setup overall was also useful for facilitating the analysis of the metadata after the end of each experiment.

3.5 Experiment 04 (Children)

This experiment involved local children during limited contact time (40 minutes) within the context of a visit to their school (on the outskirts of London) accompanied by the University students (with whom we had worked in Experiment 03). These conditions meant the content of this experiment had to be adapted as follows:

1. We changed our introductory slides, so that we could adjust the context to the particular audience of Year 6 (10-11 year old) pupils who had covered WWII in their curriculum but would also need to know about the Bloomberg excavations and TETRARCHS in a succinct and age-appropriate way (Fig. 21).

2. SP and ASG delivered the introduction and managed the discussion, SP, ASG and the University students facilitated the tagging by distributing and collecting the printed photos, as well as providing extra instruction.
3. We chose to do only Activity #1 (tagging) with the pupils, followed by brainstorming and discussion on the photos, including what they found easy or hard to tag (Fig. 22). We did not restrict pupils to work by themselves (as was the case with adult participants) and indeed they naturally compared and contrasted the photos handed to them during the activity and before the discussion. We then collected and digitised all metadata from the tagged photos.
4. For Activity #1, we distributed 50 unlaminated copies of 10 unique photos. We adjusted the margins and provided pens, so that children would write on the photographs or the margins.
5. We prepared and handed out to everyone at the end of the session a two-page summary (Fig. 23) which featured information about the Bloomberg site, the archaeological photos used during the activity, how to visit the *Mithraeum* and where to find further information, publications and resources about the site.
6. As mentioned above, we prepared an information form and an ethics form specifically for our school liaison.

Fig 21: A child-adjusted visual explanation of the main principle of the TETRARCHS project (read clockwise from top left). Graphic by Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw and Sara Perry, 2023, combining web-sourced icons (which retain their copyright).

What was easy?
What was hard?

Fig 22: The corpus of 10 photos used in Experiment 04. Photography © Museum of London and MOLA.

Museum of London Archaeology (MOLA)
Bloomberg Site Excavations of the Temple of Mithras, London

Leaflet prepared by Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw and Sara Perry
(MOLA, www.mola.org.uk)
for the TETRARCHS research project (www.tetrarchs.org): hello@tetrarchs.org
historical photography © Museum of London; all modern photography © MOLA

World War II caused extensive destruction in London. Even though this was terrible for people and buildings, it revealed some of the archaeology under what was destroyed. This made possible the excavation of a Roman temple in central London in the 1950s (this photo is from 1954). When it was being excavated, a lot of people went to see what archaeologists might find.

One of the discoveries was the head of a statue of the Roman god Mithras (this is from around 200 CE (Current Era) / AD (Anno Domini)). It was found on the last planned day of the excavation and helped archaeologists identify the temple as a place of worship for Mithras. He was worshipped by men, mostly gladiators, soldiers and merchants. We are not sure exactly what he symbolised, but we know light played a part in his secret cult and killing a bull was part of his mythical story.

Much more recently, archaeologists from Museum of London Archaeology (MOLA) continued the excavations. New buildings needed construction near Cannon Street, Mansion House and Bank stations, and MOLA cleared the ground. At the archaeological site, close to the Walbrook stream, all sorts of structures were found, like this well with wooden walls. The wood has been preserved for 2000 years!

Archaeologists also found lead pipes...

... and a very rare basket, woven with clematis (a climbing plant with beautiful flowers). The basket would have been used to carry rubbish from across the town to build up the banks of the Walbrook stream, on which the Romans built the temple.

Archaeologists also found several leather shoes of many sizes, including children's, still preserved in the mud...

...a number of small oil lamps, to light people's way in the dark...

... and more surprising finds. This is an amber bead that shows a gladiator's helmet. Maybe it was worn as a good luck charm by a child!

We also have many writings on wood from the site (they are called inscriptions). This is one of the most exciting. It was part of a stylus tablet/letter sent to a man named Mogontius (the word on the right is Mogontio = 'to Mogontius'), 'in London' (the word on the left is Londinio). This is one of three tablets where 'London' (Londinium in Latin) is written down for the first time (around 60-70 CE/AD).

Today, the reconstructed temple of Mithras is protected in the basement of the Bloomberg building in central London (EC4N 8AA). You can visit it and see its finds for yourself!

If you would like to visit the Temple of Mithras exhibition, more information can be found here:
<https://www.londonmuseums.com>
You can find school resources about it here:
<https://www.londonmuseums.com/schools/>
And read a book about the excavations here:
<https://www.museumoflondon.org.uk/whats-on/books/569976-4-0499-4284-8b-60-80c-4350a457>

Fig 23: The information handout for Year 6 pupils prepared by Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw and Sara Perry. Photography © Museum of London and MOLA.

3.6 Analysis and Methodology

As mentioned above, the three activities were designed to yield particular types of data. Throughout the design, implementation and analysis phases of these experiments, we have been informed by (and continue to process) an extensive bibliography on archaeological photography, photo elicitation as a research method, data ontologies, visual communication and photographic sequencing, narrative structures and multimodal storytelling, affect in/and heritage, codification of sensory data, participatory design - as well as scholarship on the London *Mithraeum* itself.

To extrapolate data from the completed experiments and conduct an initial analysis, ahead of codifying and creating ontologies (which will be the next stage of this aspect of TETRARCHs), we queried the data as follows:

1. We compiled the corpus of MOLA photographs and plotted the original metadata for each photograph in a spreadsheet. Such metadata varied considerably depending on the photograph, from very few words, phrases or dates which had been entered in MOLA databases to bibliographic and image captions (in the case of the published or more publicly available photographs, such as those of artefacts).
2. We digitised and compiled the tagging, phrases and passages associated with each photograph in each Activity, drawn from written and oral input.
3. We calculated the amount of use and reuse of the photographs within the corpus. In other words, we extrapolated how many times photographs had been used out of a possible number of opportunities that could have been taken. We colour-coded these photographs in our relevant spreadsheets according to the percentage of their reuse by participants in our experiments (Fig. 24).
4. We extrapolated from the content of the associated texts how the photographs had been used, e.g. as bridges between action or as examples of particular feelings or situations.
5. As Activity #3 was, of all three activities, the most extensive and richest in data, there were additional ways in which we examined the resulting narratives:
 - a. We analysed the overall themes represented in the narratives and how these were delivered and received. We compiled these data in spreadsheets and draft documents, as well as PowerPoint presentations.
 - b. We calculated the position that each photo occupied within the story arc of each narrative. We then mapped which photos were used or not used, which part of the story they were used at (Figs. 25, 31), and what function they may have had within the story, e.g. as action points or facilitators of transitions in the narrative structure. We also examined whether they fell within stereotypical or innovative uses in storytelling and photo interpretation (Fig. 26).
 - c. Finally, we examined (based on literature on visual sequencing) the interplay between individual photos and the gaps between them, commonly known in graphic design and comics parlance as 'gutters' (Fig. 27). For example, in the narrative of Fig. 27, photos #5 and #6 in the sequence (TETR-Mithr-sample 24 and TETR-Mithr-sample 31 respectively) are two different ones, but the space between them (the 'gutter') was orally elaborated with a 'bridge' that connected the two and made the sequence work ("[...] it is the middle of winter / and they uncover an ominous portal [...]"). This is important, because gutters serve as notional

unedited transcript thus far (19/7/2023), page reconstructed by ASG

Fig.26: Example of content analysis of the role of photos within a completed narrative. Photography © Museum of London and MOLA, composition by Sara Perry and Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw.

Fig.27: Sequencing mapping (gutter and closure effects) of a completed narrative (categories after McCloud 1993: 74). Photography © Museum of London. Bloomberg and MOLA, composition by Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw and Sara Perry.

3.7 Preliminary Results

These results are based on analysis done on Experiments 00-02, as indicated above: the analysis of the last two experiments is not yet complete, and so their results are not currently incorporated into the overall analysis. When complete, the rest of the experiment analyses will feed into the next stage of the process (data ontology development).

Activity #1

For Activity #1 (Fig. 28), which elicited independent tagging of photos with participants' instinctive reactions, the most popular photograph in terms of reuse and metadata was one from the initial excavations of the Mithraeum (1950s), while the least popular was a documentary photo from the recent MOLA excavations (2010s), depicting mud and parts of a wall, which would not necessarily provoke an imaginative response. There were two photographs which elicited surprising tagging: the photo of the gladiator helmet bead was characterised as resembling a gummy bear (a jelly confection), and a photo of a Roman ceramic oil lamp was associated with how pottery smells.

Emergent themes from this activity include, but are not necessarily limited to:

- feelings and mood (e.g. pride, gloomy, glory gone, dull);
- sensations (e.g. cold, damp) and associated conditions (e.g. muddy, smelly, noise, slippery);
- function (e.g. tools);
- situational/use terms (e.g. evening, 1970s, time contrast);
- actions (e.g. dance);
- user reactions, especially empathy and memory (e.g. curiosity, humour, longing);
- actions or experiences in doing archaeology (e.g. discovery, obstructions, confined);
- artefact conditions, materials and importance (e.g. complete, amber, scale, demonstrates that...);
- photography conditions (e.g. forced pose) etc.

In other words, most tagging reactions to photographs tended to be more descriptive than e.g. affective or creative (in other words they described literally what they saw in the image rather than expressing their feelings or stretching their imaginations). Some participants also knew what they perceived to be 'too much' (e.g. had been part of the excavation), so they tried to 'stop themselves' from participating as fully as they otherwise might have during Activity #1. (Note: One participant even featured in one of the photos).

Activity #2

Fig.29: Photo reuse analysis of Activity #2, for Experiments 00-02. Photography © Museum of London and MOLA, composition by Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw and Sara Perry.

In this activity (Fig. 29), which asked participants to associate particular photos with particular genres of creative outputs, the two most popular photos depicted (1) an archaeologist excavating inside a Roman wooden well, and (2) the original excavation. The least popular included a photo of an archaeologist holding a leather shoe and a photo of another archaeologist who was involved in the dismantling and recreation of one of the walls of the Mithraeum during its deconstruction and reconstruction in 2011. The most surprising reuses of photos included: a Roman drain being linked to a grime album; an archaeologist drawing on site featuring in a creative arts newsletter focused on visual representation; a chain in the mud as a subject of a poster for a theatre drama featuring Judi Dench, a revered British actress; and a Roman wooden fence preserved in mud underneath concrete pillars of modern superstructures, as the subject of an arts magazine article exploring the use of wood and concrete.

Emergent themes from this activity include, but are not necessarily limited to:

- how to... or action-oriented (e.g. make your own mosaic, find your way out, facing the gods, video games, online creative arts, experimental archaeology);
- humour (e.g. raiders of the lost bark);
- documentary or TV/film programme potential (e.g. Arctic archaeology, streets below, new discoveries, reconstructing the temple, excavation history, time hunters);
- piquing people's curiosity and reflection (e.g. CSI, the truth behind..., what happens when..., sci-fi);
- objects as symbols/iconography for media (e.g. lamp as newsletter logo);

- involvement in professional practice (girls can be archaeologists too, the industrious archaeologist, footsteps to archaeology, drawing on the past);
- object biography (the Emperor's Shoe);
- audiences (e.g. bored teenager).

In other words, these results were more focused on action or involvement, going beyond the description of the image itself to suggest new forms of engagement, opportunities, ideas, etc. There were some very imaginative and playful results, especially when explained orally by participants at the end of each activity. These predisposed participants to the more playful and collaborative group work which was at the core of the third activity.

Activity #3

The results of this activity, focusing on narrative creation and storytelling through a combination of any of the 50 photographs available, will be outlined and discussed in more detail in a subsequent report/publication, because of the complexity of the resulting datasets. Suffice it to include here some observations regarding the content and delivery of the metadata.

Generally speaking, the narratives were engaging and comprehensible in their visual and oral composition (which is important, given the extremely limited amount of time that participants had for this activity). There were fluctuations in how many visuals were used and for what purpose (some of the same photos were used in different ways across teams, see Fig. 31).

In terms of preparation, the participant groups each naturally decided to brainstorm first, then rearrange the photographs in a sequence. However, there were two team deviations of this pattern of preparation and approach to storytelling. Specifically, in the case of the creative participants of Experiment 03, some created stories based on artefact biographies (e.g. an autobiography of a Roman lamp), rather than only using the photographs (even of artefacts) as nodes in a sequential progression of human-centred action.

In the narratives of the specialists involved in Experiments 00-02, the arrangement of pictures (possibly affected (consciously or subconsciously) by principles of sequential art, like comics) followed a linear, chronological progression, rather than yielding tangents or parallel or alternative 'threads'. (It is worth noting that this is something we may wish to continue investigating - i.e., are non-archaeologists more likely to choose alternative forms of storytelling?) The action generally included several (sometimes stereotypical) tropes (a popular one was using a well as a vortex), but was also enriched with affect, e.g. empathy in terms of feelings and situations (e.g. cold, damp), either through experience or imagination. Some pictures were cast as action-related, 'protagonistic' (usually those with 'generic' people or spotlit artefacts - for example studio photography), whereas others (e.g. with no people or crowds) were 'background', scene-setting visuals (also see below).

Emergent themes include:

- imaginary steps back/flashbacks in time;
- supernatural thriller, magical properties of artefacts;
- suspense and curiosity, danger, surprise, humour, action, complicity of audience etc.

In other words, most of the story arcs were imbued with surprise/suspense/revelation.

Overall

Comparisons

TETR-Mithr-sample13 / M_059714004

TETR-Mithr-sample18 / M_10112019

Fig.30: Cumulative photo reuse analysis across activities, for Experiments 00-02 (green = high use, yellow = medium use, red = no use). Photography © Museum of London and MOLA, composition by Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw and Sara Perry.

Taking the results of photographic reuse and metadata across all three activities in Experiments 00-02 only (Fig. 30a), we can extrapolate that Activity #1 yielded the highest proportion of engagement across photos. This may be because of the nature of engagement (e.g. individual activity, silence in the room with fewer distractions, fewer photos per person), but it may also be due to the fact that these were specialists, so they were more comfortable in tagging all images. Activity #2 saw recurring associations of specific photos, but also almost a third not being used. Activity #3 again saw a third of the photographs not being used, one being used in all possible cases, but also a varied pattern of associations, even though the content of several of the narratives was not dissimilar (e.g., travelling backwards or forward in time to retrieve or replace an artefact).

Across all activities, some photos displayed consistency in their (high or low) reuse and/or associations, whereas there were a few examples of photos used in unusual ways depending on the Activity (Fig. 30b). In fact, several photos or collocations of photos and meanings can be seen to have been more frequently used at particular points within the narrative (Fig. 31). A characteristic example is a recent photo of the Mithraeum exhibition, which only occurs at the beginning (scene-setting) or the end (safe keeping) of the narrative.

Fig. 31: Photographic grouping depending on frequency of use at different parts of the story arc, for Experiments 00-02. Photography © Museum of London and MOLA, arc graphic sourced from the web (retaining its copyright), overall graphic and composition by Anna Simandiraki-Grimshaw and Sara Perry.

Commonly explored themes were sensations, emotions, identity, suspense, types of audiences, physical conditions, empathy, humour and the magical (note that magical properties appear in specialists’ stories nearly as often as in those of creatives). Issues were discussed around identity (e.g. of the people in the photos, of the participants, of the artefacts), as well as the tension between knowing and creating/imagining. For example, some participants raised a point about disambiguation of the tasks: whose emotions and reactions are being explored, the participant's or those of the person depicted in a photograph? This led to the articulation of a concern regarding the (potential) separation of fact (what the photo shows) and fiction/reactions (what we feel and interpret), especially when it might lead to unacceptable or incorrect narratives (e.g. used for misinformation or radicalised theories).

3.8 Discussion and Conclusions

Our experiments provide important grounding to hone the logic of TETRARCHS’ data model and our approach to refining data capture in the field, lab and beyond. We wish to reserve full discussion and conclusions until the remainder of our results are analysed, and after we have completed a final experiment with Bloomberg representatives, as well as more targeted experiments in both the UK and abroad. However, so far, the MOLA experiments allow us to identify vocabulary classes, especially informed by the emergent themes of Activities #1 and #2.

Perhaps more interestingly, the experiments allow us to think differently about future approaches to capturing archaeological photos - both in terms of what to capture, and how to immediately enrich those photos with storytelling metadata upon their capture.

For instance, it is clear that some photos elicit minimal or bland responses from participants, and may be used only for perfunctory, box-ticking purposes or for reinforcing problematic tropes (i.e., they are enabling an establishment that does not best serve archaeologists or citizens). With this

knowledge in mind, we can now investigate specific **questions based around field and lab practice (PQs)**:

1. Can we build field workflows & prompts that support practitioners in (i) taking more diverse photos with maximum reuse potential and (ii) reducing the taking of photos that have minimal or problematic potential? *Note: Answering this question allows us to attempt to live up to our values around mindfulness of power and empowering others; respecting and protecting the environment (reducing wasteful activities); and honouring different ways of thinking.*
2. Can we adjust our digital recording systems to support practitioners in tagging photos at the point of capture with TETRARCHs' storytelling vocabulary, with a focus on **only** the most high-potential images? *Note: Answering this question allows us to attempt to live up to our value around prioritisation of efficiency & impact.*
3. In implementing Q1 and Q2, can we observe immediate changes to or impacts on specialists' interpretations of the archaeology on site or in the lab, or to the wider interpretative process used in the field or the lab? *Note: Answering this question allows us to attempt to live up to our values around human-centredness and prioritisation of efficiency & impact.*

Moreover, the experiments have made clear that different types of photos facilitate different types of stories and different story arcs - or they enable different storytelling journeys at large. For instance, some photos play key roles in narrative transitions, even if on the surface they may not seem evocative or easily reusable. Others appear to inspire specific types of stories (e.g., historical imagery is often instinctively linked with documentary film or audio stories). Others inspire outlandish analogies which may be inaccurate, but which simultaneously create joy and humour for others - and this leads us to wonder how we can create a data model that embraces both integrity and playfulness. We also observe that archaeological specialists tend to adopt more traditional storytelling practices than those coming from more diverse creative backgrounds. With this knowledge in mind, we can structure further research around key **storytelling questions (SQs)**:

1. Can we structure our metadata in such a way that it can eventually support a number of different storytelling devices to ensure different audiences are able to reuse archaeological photos in meaningful and evocative ways? e.g., transition, emotional reaction, sensory experience, genre, etc. *Note: Answering this question allows us to attempt to live up to our value around empowering others; and being human-centred.*
2. Can this happen at the point of capture in the digital recording system in an efficient way (see PQ2)? *Note: Answering this question allows us to attempt to live up to our value around being proficient and efficient, and respecting the environment.*
3. What different approaches to storytelling with archaeological photos do we see from non-archaeologists? How and when can we most easily and fully integrate their needs and pleasures into the TETRARCHs data model whilst maintaining safe, robust and just spaces for all? *Note: Answering these questions allows us to attempt to live up to our values around being open, transparent and courageous; empowering others; and acting with dignity, respect and kindness.*

The experiments we have conducted so far offer the baseline for developing our research into (1) modifying existing archaeological practice to facilitate enhanced reuse of archaeological data, and (2)

diversifying storytelling about the past. We propose now to investigate our PQs and SQs in the following contexts:

1. PQs tested in Summer 2024, with findings integrated into revisions of the workflow and possibly tested again either in Greece or Sweden in 2025.
2. SQs tested in further experiments in Spring and Summer 2024, as well as through refinement of the data model with Antwerp and Ghent colleagues.

4. General Reflections and Future Considerations

Västra Vång

- The results of the first experiment underline the significant impact of fully integrating 3D models into various facets of archaeological discussions. This integration has been shown to have a positive impact on excavation strategies, interpretation processes and decision-making. By recording and analysing how archaeologists interact with digital archives before, during and after archaeological investigations, we were able to observe data reuse in action. This observation highlighted the crucial role of the availability of digital data, particularly in the form of 3D models, in shaping the construction of narratives and inferences. The insights gained from this experiment have proven to be incredibly valuable, contributing to our understanding of how and when reuse takes place. During the summer of 2024, this approach will be tested as part of the Toumba Serron field archaeological survey. Unlike Västra Vång, Toumba Serron involves a larger number of archaeologists working on site over a longer period of time. By starting from the conclusion obtained in Västra Vång we will set time during the excavation to record discussion sessions using the digital archive constructed using AIR during the field season 2023.
- The second experiment, conducted at Blekinge Museum, made it possible to collect annotations that, together with those from the other experiments, will be used to build classes for the Storytelling Data Model. The way the experiment was constructed and carried out was useful, although the topic (a whole set of different information from an archaeological fieldwork) was probably too broad. For this reason, in spring/summer 2024, we will develop an experiment with a similar methodology, focusing on a single monument, which will allow us to obtain a more granular and accurate set of annotations.

Toumba Serron

- The TETRARCHs team at Toumba Serron this year focused upon two key areas, commencing the project stakeholder evaluation and mapping exercise and developing the AIR tools for use within a new bespoke research environment.
- Both of these tasks remain ongoing as we prepare for follow-on work in the coming season.
- With the developmental and workflow optimisation to date having been focused upon getting data into AIR efficiently, the current plan is to build on this year's work and draw in experiences from other lines of experimentation (at Västra Vång for example - see above), to help guide the way in which AIR delivers data in order to facilitate reuse. This may involve bespoke reporting tools and mechanisms for downloading curated data packets suitable for FAIR analysis or archiving outside of the AIR system.

- One issue that is being addressed in the off season is the requirement to make the project data open access (via AIR) as close to the point of acquisition, in order that other stakeholders might be able to interact with it and guide the team in future data acquisition and the functionality of AIR. The TSRP faces some bureaucratic issues around this, as this is not a conventional practice in Greece. The project is currently seeking support from the BSA to receive permission from the Ephoria.

MOLA

- The experiments have yielded rich and sometimes surprising, but also creative reuse, reinterpretation and metadata of the corpus of the photographs.
- Apart from the creation of metadata, which will feed into data ontologies and controlled vocabularies, it has been useful to see which (kinds of) photos are reused, what they elicit and why, which requires further analysis.
- It is worth considering how, in the next stage of the project, we can analyse ethnographically the way that people collaborated, exchanged information and co-created narratives.
- Equally, it would be useful to examine and possibly systematise how the (re)use and 'character' of the photos changes, depending on the context of each activity (e.g. the drain [featuring in Fig.29] was a passing image-node in a narrative, but a protagonist in a musical genre).
- We are conscious of timing now, as we need to ensure Antwerp and Ghent colleagues are able to integrate our findings into their model, recognising some of these findings may come as late as August 2024. We need to design and conduct fieldwork in Greece in Summer 2024, and ideally revise and retest our outputs again in 2025 in Sweden if possible (or again in Greece).
- We believe the Toumba Serron ethnographer can play a key role in designing and implementing our research approach to answering PQ3 and SQ3.

TETRARCHs is making archaeological data accessible to a wider range of people.

The project explores how data from excavations and post-excavation research can be used and reused for educational, creative, and other life-enriching purposes. We work collaboratively across a variety of communities to experiment with storytelling about the past.

For heritage professionals, we create new resources for developing and measuring the effectiveness of archaeological data for storytelling.

For memory institutions like museums and cultural centres, we create reference materials to support you using these new resources for storytelling.

For creatives and local citizens, we will create a platform where you can search for and experiment with storytelling about the past.

Get in touch:

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